

PROCEEDINGS OF THE GAMES INTERSECTIONAL SYMPOSIUM

September 19 and 20, 2025

The symposium brought together artists, researchers, designers, and community organizers working at and within the intersections of games, identity, and justice.

Organized by Games Intersectional Roundtable (GIRT).
Contact us at gamesintersectional@gmail.com.

The following contributions were presented at the first GIS 25 held online in gathertown:

Social Innovation and Video Games: Exploring Implications for Learning and Teaching

by Patrick Gregori & Milica Marković, University of Klagenfurt

Sliders for Everything (Except Gender): A Critique of Gender Norms in Video Game Character Creators through 'Your Average Character Creator'

by Eileen Carette

Disruption through Strategic Game Design: Challenging Caste Transmission Using Interactive Media

by Srikanth Sundaram

In Other Bodies - Inhabiting the Nonhuman Body in Video Games as a Means for Empathy

by Florian Schäfer

For more information, visit our [website!](https://gamesintersectional.github.io/gi-symposium25/)
<https://gamesintersectional.github.io/gi-symposium25/>

Disruption through Strategic Game Design: Challenging Caste Transmission Using Interactive Media

Introduction

Caste is a centuries long system of division, oppression, segregation and violence that has led to a systemic social power imbalance in Indian history. I was raised to believe it was our pride, heritage, tradition and culture – which is the most common way it is spread and passed down generations – through indoctrination. I heard it in quiet dinner conversations, in who was invited home and who wasn't, in the way some names were said with respect, and others with disgust. I didn't know what I was learning. But I inherited a system I didn't ask for, which took me years of critical thinking to question and unlearn certain values.

This essay focuses on interrupting the oldest, most brutal and violent system of social control in Indian history. Given its close ties to religion, pride and identity, it is rarely addressed in the media. I have noticed how attempts to cull this system are met with censorship and erasure given its influence and weight in political power. Something more disturbing is that caste doesn't stop at the borders of India and travels quietly but powerfully into diasporal communities, tech jobs, elite universities, and friend circles. It survives through silence, merit rhetoric, and cultural pride and mutates into something even harder to name – but just as violent as it is.

What if strategic game design could help interrupt that cycle? This essay explores how strategic game design can challenge caste transmission – especially among youth – before casteism calcifies into unexamined identity. While older generations guard caste through pride and denial, younger generations grow up gaming, given its substantial rise in recent times. They play stories full of war, resistance, grief, loyalty, and moral choice – often unsupervised, often emotionally invested. I have found in existing literature and my previous research that media and procedural rhetoric [2] can be used to subconsciously influence harmful beliefs and ideologies [3, 7]. That space, largely unmonitored by casteist adults, is where I propose intervention to prevent the spread of a violent system that facades as culture/identity. If families buy children games filled with violence, they can survive games that tell the truth.

Brief History of the Caste System

Caste is one of the oldest and most persistent systems of birth-based hierarchy in the world. It divides people into rigid social categories from birth, assigning 'value' to human life based on lineage and occupation. It is economic, religious, sexual, and political and controls who you marry, what you eat, where you live, how you're treated, what gods you're allowed to worship, and whether your humanity is ever recognized [5]. Its ties to religious contexts has made it difficult to fight against it – despite many movements and organisations fighting for human rights.

It began as a fluid system of social roles in early Vedic texts, which categorized people into broad occupational groups. Over centuries, this system hardened into a rigid

hierarchy of purity and pollution, transforming into the birth-based structure we now know as caste. As Brahmanical power consolidated, caste became a tool to enforce control over land, labor, sexuality, and knowledge. The Manusmriti – a legal text dated around 200 BCE – explicitly codified caste as divine law, restricting education, mobility, and dignity for those deemed ‘lower’ in the hierarchy [5]. Over time, this system divided itself into thousands of sub-castes, creating hyper-local hierarchies and enforcing occupational segregation, and violence. Caste was upheld through religion, ritual humiliation, economic exclusion, and state enforcement.

The Dalit, Bahujan, and Adivasi communities – the ones forced to the bottom of this pyramid – have faced centuries of systemic exclusion, landlessness, rape, enslavement, forced labor, and erasure. Manual scavenging, caste-based lynching, segregated schooling, and access denial – despite laws against caste-based discrimination – happen covertly to this day. It survives through culture and silence. Through networks of marriage, inheritance, and shame, caste privilege remains invisible – especially in upper-caste spaces where ‘we don’t talk about caste’ often means ‘we don’t name the power we hold,’ ways which I personally have observed the system to be transferred.

Today, caste is a historical injustice that adapts, hides, and travels through silence. However, given its influence in political power, it remains largely invisible in the media. I have noticed multiple

Migration and Diaspora

Historically, Indian migration was dominated by upper-caste communities, who had greater access to education, wealth, and international opportunities. As they moved into elite institutions such as tech companies, universities, government, and NGOs, caste hierarchy quietly moved with them. It wasn’t declared given its questionable roots, but it was practiced subtly: in who was included, who was trusted, who was mocked, and who was erased. Today, as education and economic shifts have allowed more Indians across caste lines to migrate, the system persists subtly, but dangerously. In diaspora families, caste is preserved through marriage expectations, social gatekeeping, WhatsApp group gossip, and caste-coded language like ‘cultured,’ ‘respectable,’ or ‘good family background.’ In friend circles, it surfaces through exclusion such as who is left out of gatherings, who is quietly judged for how they speak or what food they eat. In elite Indian student groups, it appears as an obsession with English fluency and surnames that quietly signal caste. I have personally experienced this system travelling amidst friends as I migrated out and faced subtle exclusion and harassment. This system not only affected my social circles but disturbed me as I noticed it leaking into other people for ‘being different.’

Existing research has shown a consensus on how caste has migrated and its effects on the Indian Diasporal communities outside India [1]. Caste migration usually hides behind ‘tradition,’ and ‘values’, but it functions as a global tool of exclusion. Recent attempts to ban caste discrimination, such as in California and British Columbia were met with backlash from caste-privileged Indian communities abroad, who claimed such laws were ‘anti-Hindu’ rather than anti-oppression [4]. Invoking and intertwining religion with this brutal system made it a much more sensitive issue to tackle with law enforcement. This resistance revealed a

dangerous truth about how caste travels. It goes unnamed in the diaspora and becomes even harder to confront. That is why it is important to intervene and disrupt this dangerous system that is still covertly spreading to this day.

Personal Experiences

I am writing this essay from the lens of someone born into caste privilege and renounced it after learning the real history behind it. It is the kind that moves silently and confident that its power will go unquestioned. Like many others in the diaspora, I was raised to believe caste didn't 'exist anymore' and the questionable actions that we were made to follow was culture. It was in who we befriended, whom we excluded and in the pride families took in being 'our kind of people' and the silence around anyone who wasn't. I've witnessed caste being upheld through small, daily violences like family members calling someone 'uncultured' for their surname or dialect, refusing to eat food cooked by certain people, questioning the 'background' of a friend, or making casteist jokes behind closed doors, always followed by 'don't be so sensitive' or 'you must not question the word of god.'

In diaspora settings, this got worse as caste was hidden and defended. I've known people who subtly policed who I dated based on last names, who mocked anti-caste activists as 'radicals,' calling them blasphemous, ruined due to exposure, and who glorified their caste group as superior, all while claiming caste was irrelevant abroad. When I chose to defect from this system, it was difficult to unlearn deep rooted beliefs that were indoctrinated, as well as being met with shame and isolation. Caste survives because it goes unspoken and must be named and disrupted before it can be passed on.

In most caste-privileged households, control over culture is tight. Parents and families often monitor religion, schoolwork, friendships, and media consumption. But I've noticed video-games to be different. Gaming often slips past that intergenerational filter – titles like GTA V or Call of Duty which are all rated 18+, yet widely played by underage youth [6]. These games, often violent and morally complex, are accessed because the generational gatekeeping failed. Many parents don't fully understand the content of the games they fund. They see games as distractions or rewards instead of spaces where narrative or political learning occur, but children, especially in diasporal contexts, form deep emotional connections to games. They play without adult interpretation or cultural policing. I propose this loophole as a design opportunity to disrupt problematic ideologies – such as caste – to be transmitted down generations. Games have been able to teach players loyalty to gangs, trust in outlaws, empathy for fugitives, or resistance against empires – they can also be designed to teach resistance towards caste, given how education, information and family histories erase: discrimination, exclusion, protest, sacrifice.

The strategy I propose is to embed anti-caste ideology into mechanics and narrative arcs, – reaching young players before caste ideology calcifies given the ability of video games to subtly persuade and influence players. Existing research has identified how media – especially games can help influence beliefs [3]. However, this makes it an ethically sensitive field to navigate given the power to influence individuals before core beliefs have taken root. With responsible design, however, this strategy can help fight not just caste, but other problematic ideologies such as racism, sexism, queerphobia [7], which incidentally aligns

with one of my prior research studies. The fundamental concept used to influence and persuade beliefs is the theory of procedural rhetoric – coined by Bogost [2].

Procedural Rhetoric and Subtle Persuasion

In order to challenge caste through games, I suggest we use the concept of procedural rhetoric to design systems beyond just representation. Token characters without agency or cultural grounding do little. What we need is anti-caste game design that operates on multiple levels: narrative and mechanics to subtly persuade and influence players.

For narrative, these games must center stories that reflect the lived realities of caste-oppressed communities. These stories should draw from oral histories, ancestral trauma, and survival, without exoticizing or flattening them. They must be written with nuance and care and narratively structured to evoke and persuade against deep rooted beliefs. In my previous research, I've found that narrative framing can influence player perception especially around deeply held beliefs such as queerphobia [7]. Caste functions similarly as it excludes based on identity, often invisibly. Through structured storytelling, designers can subtly challenge the player's assumptions and create space for unlearning. If games can make players empathize with outlaws (Arthur Morgan) or war criminals (Kratos), they can absolutely teach empathy for the oppressed.

For mechanics, the idea is to model structural simulation like how survival games simulate hunger or horror games simulate fear, anti-caste games can simulate oppression and resistance that affect gameplay. For instance, Players could experience caste-based restrictions such as being unable to access wells, temples, jobs, or certain parts of the map unless they resist or disrupt the system or reputation systems could respond to defiance or solidarity – rewarding community-building, while punishing allegiance to oppressive systems, which can be woven into narrative to subtly push the idea through procedural rhetoric [2, 3, 7].

Subtle game frustrations – like NPC walking speed mismatch – are often cited as annoying. Designers can leverage this kind of mechanical friction intentionally: simulate what caste discrimination feels like. Being denied, slowed down, overlooked, restricted – all these can be designed to evoke mild player anger or discomfort. That emotion becomes a learning moment. Inducing similar mechanics that annoy, anger or openly simulate the nuanced experiences of what caste-based discrimination or violence feels like might subtly plant the seed in resistance. While this initially might not radically change beliefs, slow and subtle changes with time and absorption of content might help resist harmful beliefs.

Ethics and Risks

Designing games that challenge caste, especially as someone raised within caste privilege, I realise that will come with strong backlash. I know this because I've already lived through it. When I began rejecting caste as I distanced from family traditions – I experienced a quiet but brutal form of isolation. There's a cost to breaking with what you were supposed to inherit. This work continues that refusal. Video-games are not innocent, because just like they can teach empathy and resistance, they can also reinforce bias, celebrate supremacy, and

normalize violence. They've been used to glorify empire, war, conquest, therefore if games can be used to subtly ingrain dangerous ideologies, then they can be used to undo them too given the double edged nature of this strategy. Hence, ethical and responsible design is crucial when tackling a sensitive problem that has plagued us for centuries.

References

- [1] Gurram Ashok and Donthagani Veerababu. 2024. Indian diaspora, caste and public diplomacy: a study of digital diaspora. *South Asian Diaspora*: 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19438192.2024.2369437>
- [2] Ian Bogost. 2007. *Persuasive Games: The Expressive Power of Videogames*. MIT Press, Cambridge, MA.
- [3] Hendrik Engelbrecht, Nynke van der Laan, Renske van Enschoot, Emiel Kraahmer, Fausto Burgemeester, Spatika Gujran, and Leila Marandi. 2025. The Effect of Procedural Rhetoric and Narrative Content in a Narrative Game-Based Fear Appeal 2025. *International Journal of Serious Games* 12, 2 (2025). <https://doi.org/10.17083/ijsg.v12i2.886>
- [4] Roshni Kapur. 2024. The growing momentum and pushback against Anti-Caste politics in the diaspora. *South Asian Voices*. Retrieved from <https://southasianvoices.org/pol-f-in-n-anti-caste-politics-03-04-2024/#:~:text=Half%20of%20the%20Indian%20Americans,of%20a%20legal%20gray%20area.>
- [5] Arunoday Sana. THE CASTE SYSTEM IN INDIA AND ITS CONSEQUENCES. *International Journal of Sociology and Social Policy* 13, 3/4: 1–76. <https://doi.org/10.1108/eb013170>
- [6] None Wonsun Shin and None Jisu Huh. 2011. Parental mediation of teenagers' video game playing: Antecedents and consequences. *New Media & Society* 13, 6: 945–962. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1461444810388025>
- [7] Srikanth Sundaram. 2025. Rhetorical Empathy and Queer Affect in the Fandom of Anime and Manga. *Preprint* https://doi.org/10.31235/osf.io/smd6f_v1